

**THE LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE IN THE ARTISTIC SPEECH OF ALISHER
NAVOI**

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Abstract. This article examines the use of medical vocabulary, images, and concepts in Alisher Nava'i's literary works. It analyzes how the poet employs medical language not literally, but metaphorically, philosophically, and psychologically. It demonstrates that Nava'i's medical terminology serves as a means of understanding love, spiritual suffering, and the moral state of individuals and society. It concludes that Nava'i's poetic thought is deeply connected to the scientific concepts of his time.

Key words: Alisher Navoi, medicine, artistic language, metaphor, doctor, illness, healing.

Alisher Navoi occupies a special place in the history of Turkic literature as a poet, thinker, and humanist. His works cover a wide range of philosophical, ethical, and social issues. One little-studied aspect of his work is his use of medical language in his poetry.

During Nava'i's time, medical knowledge based on the works of Ibn Sina, al-Razi, and other Eastern scholars was part of a shared intellectual space. Therefore, the poet's recourse to medical terminology is not accidental. However, Nava'i uses the language of medicine not as a physician, but as a wordsmith, imbuing it with symbolic and metaphorical meaning.

The purpose of this article is to analyze how medical vocabulary functions in Navoi's poetry and prose and what artistic and philosophical meaning it carries.

One of the most common medical images in Navoi's poetry is illness. In his works, illness rarely signifies purely physical ailments. More often, illness symbolizes the suffering of love, spiritual anguish, and internal conflict.

In Navoi's love poetry, the enamored hero constantly refers to himself as sick, and love as an illness that defies conventional treatment. The illness, however, takes on a paradoxical character: people suffer from it, but do not desire a cure.

"My illness is incurable, because its cure is you yourself."

Here medical vocabulary is used to convey a psychological condition close to what in modern terminology might be called a psychosomatic disorder.

Navoi's image of a doctor is not only a person who heals the body. He is a symbol of reason and knowledge. image of a mentor, sometimes - a powerless observer.

In love poetry, the doctor is often contrasted with the beloved. While the doctor treats the body with medication, the beloved possesses the only "cure" for heart disease.

"The doctor knows many potions,

But he doesn't know the cure for love."

Thus, Navoi shows the limitations of a purely rational, scientific approach to the human soul.

Navoi's image of medicine has multiple meanings. It can represent a word, sight, mercy, spiritual cleansing.

The poet often emphasizes that the wrong medicine can worsen an illness. This can be seen as an allusion to human moral failings or the unjust actions of the authorities.

In this context, the language of medicine becomes a means of social criticism, where society is presented as a sick organism in need of wise and fair "treatment."

The heart occupies a special place in Navoi's artistic expression . On the one hand, it is an organ known to medicine. On the other , it is the center of feelings, faith, and suffering.

Navoi describes the heart as wounded, bleeding, weakened by disease.

These images have no anatomical significance, yet they create a vivid bodily visualization of the human internal state. Thus, the poet combines medical understanding of the body with Sufi philosophy.

Through medical vocabulary, Navoi expresses ideas of mercy and compassion. A true "doctor," in his understanding, is one who empathizes. Treatment without compassion is meaningless. This idea resonates with the ethical principles of Eastern medicine, where the physician was seen as a servant of humanity, and not just a craftsman. An analysis of Alisher Navoi's artistic language reveals that the language of medicine occupies a significant place in his poetic system. Medical imagery is used not to describe physiological processes, but as a means of expressing profound psychological, philosophical, and social ideas.

Navoi demonstrates a holistic understanding of man as a unity of body and soul. His use of the language of medicine testifies to the high level of scientific culture of the era and the poet's ability to reinterpret scientific concepts in artistic form. Thus, medical vocabulary in Navoi's works is not a secondary element, but a significant tool of artistic thinking.

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